

1 **Feed restriction in mid-lactation dairy cows: Effects on milk production and**
2 **energy and protein-related blood metabolites.**

3 I. Ansia¹, Y. Ohta², T. Fujieda², and J. K. Drackley¹

4 *¹Department of Animal Sciences, University of Illinois, Urbana 61801*

5 *²Ajinomoto Co., Inc., Tokyo, Japan.*

6 Short title: **Metabolic adaptation to feed restriction**

7 Corresponding author: James K. Drackley. 1207 W. Gregory Dr., Urbana, IL 61801.

8 drackley@illinois.edu

9

10 **Abstract**

11 The aim of the study was to describe the metabolic responses on energy and
12 protein metabolism to a period of negative nutrient balance induced by feed restriction
13 (FR). Seven multiparous Holstein cows (93 ± 15 days in milk) were randomly assigned
14 to 7 treatments in a 7×4 Youden square design. Daily intake was restricted to provide
15 60% of energy requirements during 5 d except for one treatment with ad libitum (AL)
16 feeding. While 5 out of 7 experimental treatments involved abomasal supplementation
17 of macro-nutrients, in this article we evaluated only the effects of a negative nutrient
18 balance by comparing both control treatments (AL and FR). Data of 2 cows within the
19 AL group were removed due to sickness and therefore it had $n = 2$. Milk and energy
20 corrected milk yield were reduced by FR. Yields of milk protein and lactose were lower
21 during FR than during AL but the yield of milk fat only had a tendency ($P > 0.06$) to be
22 lower with FR. Milk protein concentration was lower with FR than with AL but
23 concentration of milk lactose and fat were not different between diets. The FR induced a
24 decrease in plasma insulin and glucose concentrations, with quadratic decreasing
25 trends both reaching nadirs on d 3. Simultaneously, non-esterified fatty acids (NEFA)
26 concentration was greater and increased quadratically, peaking at d 3 during FR. There
27 were no differences in daily β -hydroxybutyrate concentration, but it increased linearly
28 until d 4 with FR. Comparison of the variation in concentration after feeding of insulin,
29 NEFA and glucose could indicate a likely increased insulin sensitivity for peripheral
30 NEFA uptake and a resistance for glucose uptake. This mechanism would contribute to
31 decrease NEFA in circulation and sparing of glucose for lactose synthesis, respectively.
32 A rapid decrease of most amino acids in plasma was paired with an increase in blood

33 urea N with its peak on d 2 and decreasing afterwards. On the other hand, Lys, Arg,
34 Gly, Gln, and Cys were greater during FR. Comparing the fluctuation of all the essayed
35 N components in circulation across the 5-d period, protein tissue mobilization may have
36 supplied amino acids for catabolism to provide needs for N and energy precursors.
37 Metabolic adaptations to a short-term reduction in dry matter intake include lipid and
38 protein tissue mobilization, as well as modulation of peripheral tissue endocrine
39 sensitivity in order to maintain yield of milk components production but prioritizing milk
40 fat and lactose over milk protein.

41 **Keywords:** lipid mobilization, protein tissue mobilization, tissue endocrine sensitivity,
42 urea.

43 **Implications**

44 The short-term feed restriction model described in this article can serve as an
45 alternative to study metabolic adaptations during the transition period. The response of
46 energy and protein metabolism observed sets the baseline to measure the effect of
47 nutrients supplementation and identify those candidates that will improve milk
48 production and overall health after calving.

49 **Introduction**

50 Homeorhetic changes in endocrine concentrations lie behind the inherent
51 decrease of dry matter intake (**DMI**) around parturition (Drackley, 1999). A reduction in
52 DMI across the transition period triggers a synchronized cascade of metabolic
53 adaptations aimed to maintain an optimal concentration of glucose in circulation and a
54 steady energy supply at the cellular level. Mobilization of stored lipids is a major

55 mechanism to provide energy at the cellular level, but an excessive use of stored lipids
56 can lead to metabolic malfunctions due to hepatic lipid accumulation and excessive
57 ketone bodies formation (Bobe et al., 2004). Therefore, availability of other precursors
58 of glucose and energy, such as amino acids (**AA**), plays a vital role during periods of
59 negative nutrient balance (**NNB**; Arriola Apelo et al., 2014).

60 Distribution and efficient use of the required amino acids (**AA**) during a period of
61 lower DMI requires an inter-organ coordination between liver and peripheral tissues
62 (Arriola Apelo et al., 2014). Amino acid uptake by the mammary gland assumes a high
63 priority because of the relative amount consumed in comparison with the splanchnic
64 tissues (Hanigan et al., 2001), and because the mammary gland is able to alter
65 extraction efficiency according to its requirements (Mephram, 1982; Mackle et al., 2000).
66 Accordingly, the negative protein balance during the transition period is reflected in
67 lower concentrations of the majority of essential and non-essential AA in circulation,
68 which eventually will recover their “pre-transition” values later during lactation (Maeda et
69 al., 2012). Nevertheless, analysis of the AA individually during the transition period can
70 sometimes lead to misleading conclusions due to the effect of different feeding or
71 grouping strategies applied (Doepel et al., 2002).

72 Feed restriction models do not simulate the natural NNB occurring during the
73 transition period. However, this model has been a valid system to identify metabolic
74 adaptations to nutrient deficiency at a molecular level, without the collateral effect of the
75 endocrine regulation characteristic of parturition and the onset of lactation (Gross and
76 Bruckmaier, 2015). The objective of this study was to characterize and quantify the
77 effects of feed restriction on energy and protein metabolism. Our hypothesis was that

78 timing and magnitude of the variation in certain blood metabolites could highlight the
79 most important metabolic pathways and accentuate requirements for specific AA in
80 maintenance of milk production and basal metabolism when DMI is deficient. Our
81 analysis sets the baseline to evaluate the effects of specific nutrient supplementation
82 within this model.

83 **Materials and methods**

84 *Animals and diets*

85 Seven rumen-cannulated multiparous Holstein cows past peak lactation (93 ± 15
86 d in milk; BW = 674 ± 43 kg) were used in a 7×4 Youden square design with 4
87 experimental periods of 10 d. Seven treatments were applied to evaluate the effects of 5
88 different abomasal infusions of macronutrients on energy and protein metabolism during
89 a 5-d feed restriction period. Only the results from the comparison of the 2 treatments
90 used as a positive (ad libitum; **AL**) and negative (feed restriction; **FR**) controls are
91 discussed in this article and will be referred to as diets. Cows during AL were fed to
92 ensure dailyorts of >15 % of the feed amount offered, and FR cows were fed to meet
93 60% of their net energy requirements for lactation (NEL) at the beginning of each period.
94 During d 1 to d 5 of each period, cows received the corresponding diet (FR or AL) plus a
95 daily 4-h abomasal infusion of distilled water (225 mL/h) beginning when the feed was
96 delivered (09.00). Infusions were administered with a rotary peristaltic pump (Sentinel
97 Enteral Feeding Pump, Alcor Scientific Inc., Smithfield, RI). During the following 5 d (d 6
98 to 10) all 7 cows were fed for ad libitum DMI to obtain 15% of refusals as fed, as a
99 recovery and wash-out period.

100 All cows were housed in tie stalls and were milked twice daily at 0600 and 1700
 101 in a parallel parlor during the duration of the trial. Milk was sampled and milk production
 102 was recorded at each milking. One aliquot of each daily milking sample was preserved
 103 (800 Broad Spectrum Microtabs II; D&F Control Systems, Inc., San Ramon, CA),
 104 refrigerated, and then analyzed (Dairy Lab Services, Dubuque, IA) for contents of fat,
 105 protein, milk urea nitrogen (**MUN**), lactose, and total solids. Another aliquot was frozen
 106 immediately at -20°C. Cows were adapted to the tie stalls and feed for 5 d before
 107 beginning the first treatment. Body weight was measured on d 1 of each period before
 108 feeding and also after the 5-d treatment on d 6 before feeding.

109 **Table 1** Ingredient composition of the ration

Item	Value
Ingredient (g/kg DM)	
Corn silage	342
Corn grain, ground	170
Soybean hulls	73
Soybean meal, solvent 47.5%	59
Alfalfa silage	55
Molasses beet sugar	51
Cottonseed fuzzy	50
Corn gluten feed	48
Wheat middlings	30
Limestone	12
Wheat straw	10
Lactation premix ¹	100

110 ¹ Contained (as-fed basis) 49% Soyplus, 16.4% Energy
 111 Booster[®], 15% ProvAAI Advantage, 8% NaOHCO₃, 3.9%
 112 Biotin, 3.8% Ca₂(PO₄)₂, 2% NaCl, 1.9%, Min/Vit premix
 113 (contained a minimum of 5% Mg, 7.5% K, 10% S, 150
 114 mg/kg of Se, 30 g/kg of Zn, 2,205 kIU/kg of Vit. A, 662.5
 115 kIU/kg of Vit. D₃, 22 kIU/kg of Vit. E, 0.5% MgO)

116

117 The diet, fed as a total mixed ration, was formulated according to the NRC (2001)
 118 requirements for a lactation diet (Tables 1). The ration was mixed daily and offered at
 119 09.00. The restricted diet (60% of the NE_L requirements) was calculated according to

120 the BW, daily milk production and composition, number of lactation, and days in milk.
 121 The same amount (DM basis) was offered during the following 5 d. Although not
 122 intended, the restricted diet provided ca. 60% of the essential AA (EAA) required as well
 123 (Table 2). The DM content of the total mixed ration was estimated daily (Koster Moisture
 124 Tester, Koster Crop Tester, Inc., Strongsville, OH; Oetzel et al., 1993) before feed
 125 delivery in an attempt to offer accurately the same relative amount of DM throughout the
 126 experiment. The total mixed ration was sampled every second day and analyzed by wet
 127 chemistry (Dairy One Cooperative Inc., Ithaca, NY); forages and concentrate
 128 components were sampled and analyzed weekly.

129 **Table 2.** Nutrient composition of the ration and content of energy,
 130 metabolizable protein, and amino acids (AA) relative to requirements on
 131 each diet.

Item	Value	% Req. ¹	
		AL	FR
Nutrient ² (% of DM)			
Crude protein	16.7	-	-
Metabolizable protein	11.3	115	57
ADF	23.4	-	-
aNDFom	33.3	-	-
NFC	35.9	-	-
Starch	23.7	-	-
Fat total	5.1	-	-
Ash	8.3	-	-
NE _L (Mcal/kg)	1.54	126	59
AA ³ (% of Metabolizable protein)			
Arg	6.65	146	80
His	2.72	134	65
Ile	4.88	118	56
Leu	7.91	99	47
Lys	6.52	108	55
Met	2.05	97	49
Phe	5.01	113	54
Thr	4.62	139	72
Trp	1.36	109	54
Val	5.53	118	57

132 ¹ Percentage of the requirement met with the ad libitum (AL) and feed-restriction (FR) diet
 133 according with the output of the AMTS software (AMTS, LLC). aNDFom = Neutral detergent
 134 fiber after amylase treatment and ashing.

135 ² Average nutrient composition calculated from the analysis of total mixed ration.

136 ³ Amino acid content based on ration description output from AMTS.

137 *Blood sampling and analysis*

138 Indwelling catheters were inserted into a jugular vein of each cow on the day
139 before d 1 of each period. During d 1 to d 5, blood samples were obtained at -1, 0, 3, 4,
140 5 and 14 h relative to feeding each day. Catheters were flushed with sterile heparinized
141 saline every 6 h between daily sampling periods and were removed on d 5 in each
142 period. Samples were transferred into evacuated tubes (BD Vacutainer, BD and Co.,
143 Franklin Lakes, NJ) containing clot activator for serum and K2EDTA for plasma. After
144 blood collection, tubes for plasma were placed on ice and tubes for serum were kept at
145 room temperature until centrifugation (~15 min). Serum and plasma were obtained by
146 centrifugation at 2,000 × g for 15 min at 4°C. Aliquots of serum and plasma were frozen
147 (-20°C) until further analysis.

148 Concentrations of non-esterified fatty acids (NEFA), β-hydroxy-butyrate (BHB),
149 total protein, albumin, total alkaline phosphatase (APT), aspartate aminotransferase
150 (AST), gamma-glutamyl transferase (GGT), total bilirubin, total cholesterol, glutamate
151 dehydrogenase (GDH), and triglycerides were determined at the University of Illinois
152 College of Veterinary Medicine diagnostic laboratory (Urbana, IL) using a Beckman
153 Coulter AU680 analyzer. Total globulin was calculated as the difference between total
154 protein and albumin. Insulin, leptin, serum amyloid A (SAA), and haptoglobin (HG)
155 concentrations were analyzed using commercial ELISA (enzyme-linked immunosorbent
156 assay) kits from Mercodia (catalog no. 10-1201-01), MyBioSource (catalog no.
157 MBS703026), and Tridelata Development Ltd. (catalog no. TP 802 and TP 801),
158 respectively.

159 Variables associated with the acute-phase response (total protein, albumin, HG,
160 SAA) and liver function (APT, AST, GGT, bilirubin, GDH, cholesterol, and triglycerides)
161 plus leptin were only analyzed in one sample (09.00) per day. The incremental changes
162 of NEFA, glucose, and insulin concentrations after feeding were calculated as the
163 difference between the basal concentration (average at -1 and 0 h) and the
164 concentration during the postprandial phase (average at +3, +4 and +5 h), expressed as
165 a percentage of the basal concentration.

166 Protein metabolism was assessed by analyzing concentrations of all EAA and
167 non-essential AA (NEAA), blood urea N (BUN), and other metabolites of the N cycle.
168 Concentrations in deproteinized plasma were measured by Ajinomoto Co., Inc. (Tokyo,
169 Japan) using an L-8900 AA analyzer (Hitachi, Tokyo, Japan). The incremental area
170 under the curve (IAUC) of the daily average across the 5-d period was calculated with
171 the trapezoid method for each AA and BUN.

172 *Statistical analysis*

173 Two cows were diagnosed with a bacterial endotoxemia and clinical mastitis,
174 respectively, both within the AL group. Due to the noticeable detrimental effect observed
175 on milk production, DMI, and other blood variables, and the influence that their data had
176 on the normality and homogeneity of the model, we decided to remove them from all
177 statistical analysis of performance and blood constituents.

178 Comparisons of all variables between treatments were made using the MIXED
179 procedure of SAS version 9.4 (SAS Institute, 2012) according to the following model:

$$Y_{ijklm} = \mu + Cow_i + (Cow \times Treatment) + Treatment_j + Period_k + Day_l + Hour_m + (Treatment \times Day) + (Treatment \times Hour) + \epsilon_{ijklm}$$

Effects of treatment, period, day, and hour were included as fixed effects in the CLASS statement while cow and the interaction cow by treatment were included as a random effects. The hour factor and its interaction with treatment were removed for variables measured only on a daily basis. The repeated fixed effect of day nested within period was used in the REPEATED statement with cow nested in treatment as the subject. Measurements of initial (d1) BW, initial milk production (kg/d), number of lactation, days in milk, and body condition score were included as covariates in the model according to their significance in explaining the variance in the model, and with their influence on the Bayesian and Akaike criteria. For each variable with equal time spacing between samples (e.g. milk, albumin, etc.), the subject was tested using 3 different covariance structures: autoregressive order 1, compound symmetry, and spatial power. For variables with unequal spacing (e.g. AA, NEFA, etc), spatial power law, Gaussian, and spherical covariance structures were tested. The covariance structure that resulted in the smallest Bayesian and corrected Akaike information criterion (AIC_c) was chosen (Littell et al., 2006). The degrees of freedom were estimated with the Kenward-Roger specification in the model statement.

A set of covariates was created and included to account for the carry-over effect between consecutive treatments on each variable. Covariates were retained in the model unless a 50% increase in BIC or AIC_c occurred or the normality of the residuals was disturbed. The CONTRAST statement was used to compare AL and FR. When the *P*-value of the interaction between treatment and day factors was lower than 0.1, the

203 SLICE statement was applied in order to identify the specific significant interactions for
204 each treatment for further discussion. The linear and quadratic trends were evaluated
205 using the ESTIMATE statement from PROC MIXED, to classify the evolution of the daily
206 average across the period.

207 The PROC UNIVARIATE and the INFLUENCE option within PROC MIXED were
208 applied to each variable to check for normality of residuals and for the presence of
209 outliers. Graph plots and *P*-values from the Shapiro-Wilk and Kolmogorov-Smirnov tests
210 were used to evaluate both homogeneity and normality of residuals. When appropriate,
211 variables were transformed to accomplish the above-mentioned criteria. The proper
212 power transformation was selected according with the convenient lambda displayed by
213 the TRANSREG procedure. Non-transformed LSMEANS and SEM were reported.

214 As a complementary analysis to simplify detection of interrelationships among *N*
215 compounds involved in protein metabolism, we performed factor analysis using PROC
216 FACTOR in SAS after standardization of the data set. We used the principal component
217 method to estimate the number of parameters, and the varimax rotation for a clearer
218 interpretation of the factor loadings. The final number of factors is selected by
219 dimensionality assessment according with the Kaiser's criterion eigenvalue > 1.00 and
220 graphically according with the scree plot generated by this procedure. A factor loading
221 was considered for discussion only when higher than a cut-off value of 0.5. When a
222 variable belonged to more than one factor, it was included in the one where it had the
223 greater loading.

224

225 **Table 3** Least square means of dry matter intake, energy balance, BW gain,
 226 milk production and composition of mid-lactation dairy cows during 5 days on
 227 the ad libitum (AL) and feed-restricted (FR) diets.

Item	Diet		SEM ¹	P-values		
	AL	FR		Diet ²	Day	Trt x Day ³
Dry matter intake, kg/d	25.5	12.7	1.15	<0.01	<0.01	0.01
Energy balance ⁴ (Mcal/d)	2.5	-12.9	2.4	<0.01	<0.01	0.17
BW gain ⁵ , kg/d	0.7	-13.3	0.04	0.03	--	--
<i>Yield, kg/d</i>						
Milk	39.1	30.9	1.94	<0.01	<0.01	0.05
ECM ⁶	42.6	31.9	3.30	0.02	<0.01	0.33
Protein	1.20	0.90	0.05	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
Fat	1.56	1.20	0.13	0.06	0.52	0.37
Lactose	1.82	1.39	0.09	<0.01	<0.01	0.03
Total solids	6.60	5.18	0.30	<0.01	<0.01	0.08
<i>Milk composition</i>						
Protein, %	3.11	2.95	0.05	0.04	<0.01	0.10
Fat, %	3.27	4.20	0.32	0.15	<0.01	0.24
Lactose, %	4.64	4.60	0.05	0.78	<0.01	0.34
Total solids, %	16.7	16.8	0.33	0.81	0.16	0.19
Milk urea N, mg/kg	136	140	12.4	0.82	<0.01	0.82

228 ^{1,3} SEM and treatment by day interaction p-value belong to the comparison between the seven
 229 treatments.

230 ²P-value of the orthogonal contrast between the ad libitum (AL) and feed restricted (FR) diets.

231 ⁴Energy balance = NE_L intake (Mcal) – (ECM × 3.14 + 0.293 × kg of BW^{0.75})

232 ⁵BW gain between from d 1 to d 5 on each experimental period.

233 ⁶ECM (kg) = (0.038 × g of fat + 0.024 × g of protein + 0.017 × g of lactose) × kg of milk/3.14.

234

235 Results

236 *Milk production and composition*

237 Feed restriction reduced ($P_{\text{Diet}} < 0.01$) DMI by approximately 50 % for the FR diet
 238 in comparison with AL (Table 3). Consequently, BW difference ($P_{\text{Diet}} = 0.03$), milk yield
 239 ($P_{\text{Diet}} < 0.01$) and energy corrected milk (**ECM**: $P_{\text{Diet}} = 0.02$) were reduced during FR as
 240 well. Milk protein percentage ($P_{\text{Diet}} = 0.04$), and milk protein ($P_{\text{Diet}} < 0.001$) and lactose
 241 yields ($P_{\text{Diet}} < 0.01$) were lower with FR than AL. On the other hand, milk fat yield had a
 242 tendency ($P_{\text{Diet}} = 0.06$) to be lower with FR than AL. The total solids yield of FR was

243 lower ($P_{\text{Diet}} < 0.01$) than AL. Milk yield and concentrations and yields of protein and
244 lactose showed an interaction of FR with day and all manifested a decreasing linear
245 trend across the 5-d period except total solids percentage, which tended to decrease
246 quadratically (Table 4).

247 *Energy-related metabolites and hormones in blood*

248 Cows during FR had greater NEFA ($P < 0.001$), and lower insulin ($P = 0.01$) and
249 glucose ($P = 0.04$) concentrations than cows during AL (Table 5). The restricted diet
250 decreased glucose ($P_{\text{FR} \times \text{Day}} < 0.001$) and insulin ($P_{\text{FR} \times \text{Day}} < 0.001$) concentrations in a
251 quadratic manner, reaching a nadir on d 3 (Table 6). The glucose-to-insulin (GIR) ratio
252 was greater ($P_{\text{Diet}} = 0.01$) and increased ($P_{\text{FR} \times \text{Day}} < 0.01$) linearly only during FR.
253 Concentration of NEFA increased ($P_{\text{FR} \times \text{Day}} < 0.001$) quadratically with its peak on d 3.
254 Even though we did not observe an effect of diet on BHB ($P_{\text{Diet}} = 0.33$) or leptin ($P_{\text{Diet}} =$
255 0.52), serum BHB tended to increase linearly ($P_{\text{FR} \times \text{Day}} = 0.09$) during FR. Within day,
256 we found that hour relative to feeding had an effect on all the variables in this group with
257 no differences between diets (Table 5). Concentrations of NEFA and glucose were
258 lower in the samples collected during the postprandial phase (+3, +4, +5 h relative to
259 feeding) in comparison with those pre-feeding (-1 and 0 h) and at night (+14 h), while
260 insulin and BHB were higher (Figure 1). Changes in insulin concentration after feeding
261 tended ($P_{\text{Diet}} = 0.14$) to be greater during FR, whereas changes in NEFA were
262 significantly larger ($P_{\text{Diet}} < 0.01$) and changes in glucose did not vary ($P_{\text{Diet}} = 0.46$)
263 between diets.

264

265 **Table 4.** Least square means of dry matter intake, energy balance, BW gain, milk production and
 266 composition of mid-lactation dairy cows during 5 days on the ad libitum (AL) and feed-restricted
 267 (FR) diets per day.

Item	Diet	Day					SEM	Diet x Day ¹	P-values Trends ²	
		1	2	3	4	5			Lin.	Quad.
DMI, kg/d	AL	24.5 ^b	25.2 ^b	28.1 ^a	27.5 ^a	22.0 ^c	1.3	<0.01	0.34	<0.01
	FR	12.7	12.7	12.7	12.7	12.6	1.1	1.00	0.40	0.34
<i>Yield, kg/d</i>										
Milk	AL	37.4	39.1	40.4	40.8	37.7	2.5	0.49	0.76	0.11
	FR	35.1 ^a	33.1 ^a	30.8 ^{ab}	28.7 ^{bc}	26.7 ^c	1.9	0.01	<0.01	0.99
ECM	AL	39.8	40.9	44.5	42.9	39.8	3.9	0.96	0.85	0.26
	FR	40.1 ^a	33.8 ^{ab}	30.8 ^{ab}	28.9 ^b	26.8 ^b	2.9	0.02	<0.01	0.27
Protein	AL	1.13	1.20	1.26	1.26	1.14	0.07	0.15	0.74	0.02
	FR	1.08 ^a	1.00 ^a	0.88 ^b	0.80 ^c	0.72 ^c	0.05	<0.01	<0.01	0.74
Fat	AL	1.43	1.45	1.66	1.52	1.43	0.22	0.95	0.92	0.46
	FR	1.56	1.23	1.13	1.08	1.01	0.15	0.45	0.02	0.26
Lactose	AL	1.77	1.84	1.88	1.88	1.76	0.12	0.67	0.94	0.16
	FR	1.66 ^a	1.53 ^a	1.39 ^b	1.26 ^c	1.10 ^d	0.09	<0.01	<0.01	0.83
Total solids	AL	6.54	6.54	6.89	6.76	6.28	0.42	0.64	0.84	0.25
	FR	5.86 ^a	5.72 ^a	5.21 ^{ab}	4.79 ^{bc}	4.32 ^c	0.34	<0.01	<0.01	0.55
<i>Milk composition</i>										
Protein, g/kg	AL	3.06	3.11	3.16	3.14	3.07	0.07	0.53	0.84	0.10
	FR	3.14 ^a	3.07 ^a	2.91 ^b	2.85 ^{bc}	2.79 ^c	0.06	<0.01	<0.01	0.46
Fat, g/kg	AL	3.96	2.97	3.33	3.00	3.08	0.60	0.41	0.39	0.48
	FR	3.57	4.27	4.33	4.45	4.38	0.47	0.62	0.26	0.36
Lactose, g/kg	AL	4.65	4.65	4.59	4.55	4.61	0.09	0.60	0.45	0.49
	FR	4.73 ^a	4.65 ^{ab}	4.58 ^b	4.45 ^c	4.43 ^c	0.07	<0.01	<0.01	0.67
Total solid, g/kg	AL	17.3	16.5	16.8	16.4	16.5	0.5	0.28	0.21	0.42
	FR	16.8 ^{ab}	17.1 ^a	16.9 ^{ab}	16.9 ^a	16.2 ^b	0.4	0.05	0.17	0.10
MUN, mg/kg	AL	13.3	12.9	14.1	14.3	13.6	1.7	0.94	0.75	0.75
	FR	11.8 ^b	15.7 ^a	15.1 ^{ab}	14.3 ^{ab}	13.1 ^{ab}	1.4	0.08	0.79	0.01

268 ¹P-value of the interaction of each diet (AL and FR) with day. Extracted from the SLICE statement output within the interaction of
 269 treatment with day.

270 ²P-values of the test for linear or quadratic trends.

271 Means in a row with superscripts without a common letter differ, $P \leq 0.05$.

272

273 *Acute-phase response*

274 Concentrations of albumin during FR were reduced ($P_{\text{Diet}} = 0.01$; Supplementary

275 Table S1) following a quadratic ($P_{\text{Quad.}} = 0.03$) decline across the period with its nadir on

276 d 3 (Supplementary Table S2). Concentration of HG in AL had an interaction with day

277 ($P_{FR \times Day} = 0.03$) because its concentration on d 5 was higher than during the previous 4
 278 d.

279 *Liver function variables*

280 Among all the variables that describe liver function, we only found a profound
 281 effect of the restricted diet on bilirubin ($P_{Diet} = 0.02$) and triglycerides ($P_{Diet} = 0.02$),
 282 which were elevated in plasma during FR (Supplementary Table S1). Despite an
 283 absence of interaction between diet and day effects during FR (Supplemental Table
 284 S2), triglycerides and bilirubin had ($P_{Quad.} = 0.01$) or tended to have ($P_{Quad.} = 0.12$) a
 285 quadratic progression with their peak on d 3, respectively. Similarly, APT ($P_{Linear} = 0.07$)
 286 and GDH ($P_{Linear} = 0.04$) also manifested marked decreasing linear trends.

287 **Table 5.** Least square means of the concentrations of blood metabolites associated
 288 with energy metabolism of mid-lactation dairy cows during 5 days on the ad libitum (AL)
 289 and feed-restricted (FR) diets.

Item ¹	Diet			P - values				
	AL	FR	SEM	Diet ²	Day	Trt x Day ³	Hour	Trt x Hour ⁴
NEFA, mM	0.13	0.31	0.07	0.02	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.91
NEFA change ⁵ , %	-21	-67	6.7	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	-	-
Insulin, µg/L	0.63	0.44	0.10	0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.98
Insulin change ⁵ , %	68	144	0.5	0.14	<0.01	<0.01	-	-
Glucose, mg/dL	64.7	59.9	2.1	0.04	<0.01	0.01	<0.01	0.95
Glucose change ⁵ , %	-3.67	-1.51	0.02	0.47	<0.01	<0.01	-	-
GIR	0.18	0.46	0.11	0.01	<0.01	<0.01	-	-
BHB, mM	0.60	0.58	0.12	0.33	<0.01	0.03	<0.01	0.96
Cholesterol, mg/dL	192	190	6	0.68	<0.01	0.46	-	-
Triglycerides, mg/dL	7.14	10.62	0.90	0.02	<0.01	0.91	-	-
Leptin, ng/dL	49.7	48.7	1.4	0.52	<0.01	0.01	-	-

290 ¹NEFA = non-esterified fatty acid; GIR = glucose to insulin ratio, calculated upon the pre-feeding values only (-1
 291 and 0 h).

292 ²P-value of the orthogonal contrast between the ad libitum (AL) and feed restricted (FR) diets.

293 ^{3,4}P-value of the interactions (Treatment by Day and by Hour) belong to the comparison between the seven
 294 treatments.

295 ⁵Calculated as the difference between the average of the pre-feeding values (-1 and 0 h) and the average of the post-
 296 feeding values (+3, +4 and +5 h), as a percentage of the pre-feeding values.

297

298 *Protein-related blood metabolites*

299 The FR diet reduced daily plasma concentrations of Asp ($P_{\text{Diet}} < 0.01$), Tyr ($P_{\text{Diet}} < 0.01$),
300 Pro ($P_{\text{Diet}} = 0.01$), and tended to reduce it for Thr ($P_{\text{Diet}} = 0.08$), His ($P_{\text{Diet}} = 0.06$) and Glu
301 ($P_{\text{Diet}} = 0.07$; Table 7). Despite a lack of diet effect, concentrations of other AA such as
302 Ala, Ser, Ile, Val, Trp, Asn, and Met also decreased ($P_{\text{FR} \times \text{Day}} \leq 0.01$) across days only
303 during FR (Table 8). All these AA showed or tended to show a quadratic decline,
304 whereas for Asp, Ile and Met the decrease was linear. Contrarily, plasma concentration
305 was higher during FR for Arg ($P_{\text{Diet}} = 0.05$) and tended to be higher for Gly ($P_{\text{Diet}} = 0.09$),
306 and Lys ($P_{\text{Diet}} = 0.10$). Concentrations of individual AA were lower during the
307 postprandial sampling (data not shown). Only the NEAA showed a significant decrease
308 (Figure 1). There were no differences among diets except for Glu, which was higher
309 after feeding (data not shown).

310 Ammonia (NH_3) concentration in plasma was higher ($P_{\text{Diet}} = 0.04$) in FR than
311 during AL (Table 9). Concentrations of ornithine decreased linearly across days ($P_{\text{FR} \times$
312 $\text{Day}} < 0.01$) while citrulline and BUN ($P_{\text{FR} \times \text{Day}} < 0.01$) increased, all manifesting quadratic
313 increases while their concentration during AL diet remained constant (Table 10).
314 Concentrations of ornithine, citrulline, and NH_3 were lower after feeding, whereas BUN
315 was higher after feeding regardless of the diet consumed (data not shown).

316 **Table 6.** Least square means of the concentrations of blood metabolites associated with energy
 317 metabolism of mid-lactation dairy cows during 5 days on the ad libitum (AL) and feed-restricted
 318 (FR) diets per day.

Item ²	Diet	Day					SEM	P-values		
		1	2	3	4	5		Diet x Day ³	Trend ¹	
								Lin.	Quad.	
NEFA, mM	AL	0.11	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.16	0.06	0.25	0.98	0.58
	FR	0.13 ^c	0.30 ^b	0.40 ^a	0.37 ^{ab}	0.33 ^{ab}	0.06	<0.01	0.01	<0.01
Insulin, µg/L	AL	0.60	0.75	0.72	0.59	0.51	0.12	0.38	0.32	0.07
	FR	0.81 ^a	0.50 ^b	0.30 ^c	0.29 ^c	0.31 ^b	0.10	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
Glucose, mg/dL	AL	65.4	65.7	63.5	63.8	65.2	2.5	0.72	0.73	0.40
	FR	65.2 ^a	60.6 ^b	57.4 ^c	58.1 ^{bc}	58.2 ^{bc}	2.0	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
GIR	AL	0.18	0.16	0.18	0.18	0.21	0.15	0.95	0.85	0.86
	FR	0.11 ^c	0.33 ^b	0.59 ^a	0.53 ^a	0.74 ^a	0.11	<0.01	<0.01	0.29
B-hydroxy-butyrate, mM	AL	0.63	0.64	0.64	0.55	0.57	0.14	0.65	0.57	0.77
	FR	0.52 ^{ab}	0.51 ^a	0.54 ^a	0.68 ^b	0.65 ^b	0.10	0.09	0.09	0.68
Cholesterol, mg/dL	AL	193	197	190	191	193	8	0.84	0.83	0.88
	FR	188 ^{ab}	184 ^b	190 ^{ab}	190 ^{ab}	198 ^a	6	0.20	0.19	0.26
Triglycerides, mg/dL	AL	6.35	7.08	7.58	7.08	7.58	1.54	0.98	0.63	0.79
	FR	6.80 ^b	11.95 ^a	12.70 ^a	11.70 ^a	9.95 ^{ab}	1.25	0.02	0.13	<0.01
Leptin, ng/dL	AL	4.76	4.93	5.10	5.14	4.91	0.21	0.46	0.38	0.17
	FR	4.84	4.92	4.94	4.87	4.78	0.17	0.87	0.74	0.40

319 ^{a,b,c}Means in a row with superscripts without a common letter differ, $P \leq 0.05$.

320 ¹ P-values of the test for linear or quadratic trends.

321 ²NEFA = non-esterified fatty acid; GIR = glucose to insulin ratio, calculated upon the pre-feeding values only (-1 and 0 h).

322 ³P-value of the interaction of each diet (AL and FR) with day. Extracted from the SLICE statement output within the interaction of treatment with
 323 day.

324

325

326 Other AA such as α -amino adipic acid (**α -AAA**; $P_{\text{Diet}} = 0.11$) and amines such as
327 ethanolamine ($P_{\text{Diet}} = 0.12$) tended to have greater concentrations during FR
328 (Supplementary Table S3). There was an interaction of FR with day on the daily
329 concentrations of 3-methylhistidine (**3-MH**; $P_{\text{FR} \times \text{Day}} < 0.01$), sarcosine ($P_{\text{FR} \times \text{Day}} < 0.01$),
330 phosphoethanolamine (**PEA**; $P_{\text{FR} \times \text{Day}} = 0.08$), and α -amino butyric acid (**α -ABA**; $P_{\text{FR} \times$
331 $\text{Day}} < 0.01$), all showing increasing linear trends as the period advanced (Supplementary
332 Table S4). Among these components, we found a significant hour effect for 1- (1-MH)
333 and 3-MH ($P_{\text{Hour}} = 0.01$), carnosine ($P_{\text{Hour}} < 0.01$), cystathionine ($P_{\text{Hour}} = 0.02$), taurine
334 ($P_{\text{Hour}} < 0.01$), and α -ABA ($P_{\text{Hour}} = 0.02$), all of which had lower concentrations after
335 feeding, and PEA ($P_{\text{Hour}} = 0.05$) that was higher relative to feeding time (data not
336 shown).

337 *Exploratory factor analysis*

338 The principal variables ($n = 25$) associated with protein metabolism (EAA and NEAA,
339 BUN, NH_3 , and 3-MH as indicator of protein turnover) were reduced to 5 factors that
340 explained 82.2 % of the variance in our data set (Table 11). Factor 1 is a measure of all
341 the EAA except Lys and Arg, plus Ser, Ala, Tyr, Asn, and Pro. Lysine and Arg were
342 correlated with Factor 2 while BUN, 3-MH, and Cit were correlated with Factor 3. Factor
343 4 was correlated positively with Cys and negatively with NH_3 , Glu, and Asp. Lastly,
344 factor 5 was driven mainly by Gln, Orn, and Gly.

345

346 **Table 7.** Least squares means of the concentrations ($\mu\text{mol/dL}$) of blood
 347 amino acids of mid-lactation dairy cows during 5 days on the ad libitum
 348 (AL) and feed-restricted (FR) diets.

Item	Diet			<i>P</i> – values ¹				
	AL	FR	SEM	Diet ²	Day	Trt x Day	Hour	Trt x Hour
Ala	20.4	18.0	1.5	0.23	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.7
Arg	6.33	7.57	0.5	0.05	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
Asn	4.07	3.75	0.52	0.28	<0.01	0.02	<0.01	0.59
Asp	0.48	0.39	0.05	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.33
Cys	0.07	0.08	0.03	0.13	<0.01	<0.01	0.1	0.97
Gln	24.5	27.5	1.8	0.15	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.23
Glu	4.26	3.79	0.21	0.07	0.11	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
Gly	29.6	37.3	3.6	0.09	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.99
His	5.51	4.86	0.22	0.06	<0.01	<0.01	0.05	0.99
Ile	10.5	10.1	1.0	0.54	<0.01	0.02	0.05	0.97
Leu	21.2	18.8	1.9	0.15	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.99
Lys	5.29	6.4	1.03	0.1	<0.01	0.02	<0.01	<0.01
Met	2.04	1.94	0.17	0.38	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.56
Phe	4.77	4.13	0.3	0.17	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.96
Pro	9.64	7.99	0.93	0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.99
Ser	8.15	7.91	0.63	0.71	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.99
Thr	7.67	6.37	0.56	0.08	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.94
Trp	3.07	2.8	0.21	0.32	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.88
Tyr	6.1	4.27	0.33	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.97
Val	25.3	24.2	2.7	0.24	<0.01	<0.01	0.19	<0.01
EAA	88.1	80.7	6.4	0.13	<0.01	<0.01	0.18	<0.01
NEAA	114	116	6	0.86	<0.01	0.33	<0.01	0.91

349 ¹*P*-value of the interactions (Treatment by Day and by Hour) belong to the comparison between the seven
 350 treatments.

351 ²*P*-value of the orthogonal contrast between the ad libitum (AL) and feed restricted (FR) diet.

352

353 **Discussion**

354 *Milk production and composition*

355 Dry matter intake is the main factor that drives milk production; consequently, the
356 reduction in milk production (-21%) and ECM (-25%) during FR was expected. The
357 decrease in milk was smaller than the percentage in DMI reduction (-50%), which
358 seems to indicate that metabolic adaptations were able to cope with the decreased
359 intake. The availability of NEFA from fat mobilization (Contreras et al., 2016), the lower
360 duodenal AA flux (Doepel et al., 2004), and the countervailing hormonal adjustments
361 (Arriola Apelo et al., 2014) may have resulted in the alteration of milk composition
362 during FR. We found that milk protein synthesis decreased in favor of milk fat, while
363 lactose percentage was maintained despite the drop in blood glucose concentration.
364 The marked decrease in protein synthesis is in agreement with Loores et al. (2007) who
365 found that genes that regulate protein synthesis are one of the largest category
366 downregulated during ketosis induced by feed restriction during the early postpartum.
367 Abundance of transcripts of the major proteins in milk protein is not influenced during
368 short periods of restricted energy supply, but is dependent on the transcription factors
369 regulated by the endocrine system and nutrient supply (Sigl et al., 2014).

370 There was a lack of effect of the restricted diet on milk lactose percentage while
371 plasma concentrations of its principal precursor glucose were reduced. This effect
372 could imply that other anabolic mechanisms were promoting lactose synthesis
373 (Lemosquet et al., 2009). Such mechanisms could include driving glucose towards
374 glycolysis and lactose synthesis instead of its incorporation into milk fatty acids

375 **Table 8.** Least squares means of the concentrations ($\mu\text{mol/dL}$) of blood amino acids of mid-
 376 lactation dairy cows during 5 days on the ad libitum (AL) and feed-restricted (FR) diets per day.

Item	Diet	Day					SEM	P-values		
		1	2	3	4	5		Diet x Day ³	Trends ²	
								Lin.	Quad	.
Ala	AL	22.5	21.1	20.9	18.9	18.5	1.74	0.41	0.02	0.94
	FR	21.6 ^a	16.8 ^b	16.8 ^b	17.7 ^b	17.1 ^b	1.19	<0.01	0.01	<0.01
Arg	AL	6.79	6.43	6.27	5.94	6.23	0.62	0.64	0.19	0.43
	FR	7.43	7.49	7.49	7.93	7.53	0.48	0.68	0.45	0.64
Asn	AL	4.19	4.39	4.45	4.24	3.87	0.39	0.65	0.46	0.17
	FR	5.06 ^a	3.68 ^b	3.41 ^b	3.58 ^b	3.15 ^b	0.33	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
Asp	AL	0.47	0.46	0.51	0.47	0.52	0.06	0.76	0.48	0.9
	FR	0.51 ^c	0.44 ^{bc}	0.36 ^{ab}	0.31 ^a	0.31 ^a	0.05	<0.01	<0.01	0.41
Cys	AL	0.08 ^a	0.09 ^a	0.05 ^b	0.05 ^c	0.07 ^b	0.03	<0.01	0.24	0.21
	FR	0.08 ^a	0.08 ^a	0.07 ^b	0.08 ^a	0.09 ^a	0.02	0.01	0.44	0.15
Gln	AL	25	24.2	25.2	24.5	23.6	2.1	0.78	0.65	0.64
	FR	27.4 ^a	25.7 ^b	27.6 ^a	28.6 ^a	28.1 ^{ab}	1.59	0.09	0.28	0.61
Glu	AL	4.2	4.38	4.18	4.09	4.47	0.26	0.37	0.67	0.45
	FR	4.16 ^a	3.71 ^b	3.71 ^b	3.60 ^b	3.77 ^b	0.2	0.01	0.04	0.01
Gly	AL	30.9	29.6	29.5	29.8	27.9	3.98	0.81	0.54	0.91
	FR	35.6 ^a	35.4 ^b	36.6 ^b	41.4 ^b	37.4 ^b	3	<0.01	0.16	0.39
His	AL	5.67 ^a	5.90 ^a	5.80 ^a	5.46 ^a	4.74 ^b	0.34	0.01	0.03	0.01
	FR	5.93 ^a	4.75 ^b	4.42 ^c	4.65 ^{bc}	4.52 ^{bc}	0.26	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
Ile	AL	11.7	11.1	10.8	9.5	9.3	1.1	0.3	0.03	0.91
	FR	11.4 ^a	10.0 ^b	9.7 ^b	10.0 ^b	9.3 ^b	0.9	0.01	0.03	0.25
Leu	AL	22.8	22.5	22.2	19.9	18.5	2.1	0.21	0.03	0.31
	FR	23.3 ^a	18.6 ^b	17.5 ^b	17.9 ^b	16.7 ^b	1.6	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
Lys	AL	6.16	5.41	5.19	4.79	5.01	1.28	0.55	0.44	0.58
	FR	6.54	6.31	6.15	6.7	6.29	0.8	0.36	0.96	0.88
Met	AL	2.11	2.14	2.22	1.89	1.88	0.2	0.42	0.07	0.26
	FR	2.23 ^a	1.89 ^{bc}	1.91 ^{bc}	1.92 ^b	1.78 ^c	0.14	<0.01	<0.01	0.2
Phe	AL	5.13	5	4.8	4.3	4.64	0.42	0.23	0.07	0.47
	FR	5.14 ^a	3.95 ^b	3.70 ^b	3.92 ^b	3.95 ^b	0.33	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
Pro	AL	9.91	9.85	10.18	9.62	8.65	0.97	0.32	0.21	0.15
	FR	9.78 ^a	7.73 ^b	7.41 ^b	7.88 ^b	7.17 ^b	0.73	<0.01	<0.01	0.01
Ser	AL	8.42	8.59	8.56	8.07	6.93	0.75	0.12	0.1	0.05
	FR	9.06 ^a	7.65 ^{bc}	7.31 ^c	7.93 ^b	7.44 ^{bc}	0.56	<0.01	0.1	0.05
Thr	AL	7.79	7.73	7.99	7.61	7.25	0.67	0.79	0.47	0.42
	FR	7.85 ^a	5.82 ^b	5.83 ^b	6.35 ^b	6.00 ^b	0.53	<0.01	0.01	<0.01
Trp	AL	3.12	2.98	2.99	3.06	3.22	0.24	0.69	0.59	0.18
	FR	3.21 ^a	2.83 ^b	2.63 ^b	2.73 ^b	2.63 ^b	0.18	<0.01	<0.01	0.01
Tyr	AL	6.4	6.45	6.39	5.76	5.53	0.45	0.69	0.11	0.38
	FR	6.76 ^a	4.54 ^b	3.57 ^c	3.39 ^{cd}	3.08 ^d	0.32	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
Val	AL	29.5	28.7	28.9	26.6	24.7	3.4	0.31	0.14	0.4
	FR	28.8 ^a	23.0 ^b	21.5 ^b	22.3 ^b	21.8 ^b	2.5	<0.01	0.01	<0.01
NEAA	AL	120	116	117	112	107	8	0.54	0.16	0.62
	FR	125 ^a	110 ^b	112 ^{ab}	119 ^{ab}	112 ^{ab}	6	<0.01	0.26	0.09
EAA	AL	93.8	91.5	91.5	83.7	80	7.4	0.34	0.05	0.51
	FR	96.1 ^a	78.9 ^b	75.1 ^b	78.4 ^b	75.2 ^b	6.2	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

377 ¹P-value of the interaction of each diet (AL and FR) with day. Extracted from the SLICE statement output within the interaction of
 378 treatment with day.

379 ² P-values of the test for linear or quadratic trends.

380 Means in a row with superscripts without a common letter differ, $P \leq 0.05$.

381 (Chaiyabutr et al., 1980), or by a greater insulin resistance in insulin sensitive tissue that
382 would allow higher uptake by the mammary gland (Gross et al., 2011).

383 *Lipid mobilization and insulin sensitivity*

384 The synchrony of the decline in daily concentrations of insulin and glucose, with
385 the increase of NEFA and triglycerides in circulation indicates that d 3 was the inflection
386 time point where metabolic homeostasis seemed to reach a stable state. Lipolysis of
387 triglycerides in excess of re-esterification of NEFA within adipocytes is the source of
388 NEFA in blood during periods of fat mobilization, and both processes are regulated by
389 the antilipolytic effect of insulin (De Koster and Opsomer, 2013). These two compounds
390 (NEFA and insulin) also reacted to feeding but in opposite directions, with no
391 differences between diets. However, we found a difference in the magnitude of the
392 increases in insulin (2x greater than AL), against the decreasing changes in NEFA (6x
393 greater than AL) after feeding during the FR diet. This contrast may reflect a different
394 muscle and adipose tissue sensitivity to insulin depending on the nutritional or energy
395 balance status (Marett et al., 2018a), and also may provide evidence that mammary
396 uptake of NEFA is proportional to plasma arterial concentrations (Miller et al., 1991).
397 Similar conclusions were deduced by Piantoni et al. (2015) who found no variations of
398 NEFA 4 h after feeding in cows in late lactation, but a marked effect in cows during their
399 post-partum period. The different reactions between insulin and NEFA revealed that
400 lipolytic and antilipolytic mechanisms are heavily influenced by the hourly feeding
401 behavior (Allen et al., 2005). Furthermore, the endocrine sensitivity of tissues (Ramos-
402 Roman et al., 2012) has more relevance than hormone concentration during periods of
403 NNB other than the postpartum (Gross and Bruckmaier, 2015).

404 **Table 9.** Least squares means of the concentrations ($\mu\text{mol/dL}$) of blood
 405 metabolites related with urea cycle and protein tissue mobilization of mid-
 406 lactation dairy cows during 5 days on the ad libitum (AL) and feed-restricted
 407 (FR) diets.

Item ¹	Diet			<i>P</i> – values ²				
	AL	FR	SEM	Diet ³	Day	Trt x Day	Hour	Trt x Hour
1-MH	1.02	0.97	0.09	0.99	<0.01	0.3	0.01	0.89
3-MH	0.19	0.24	0.07	0.87	<0.01	<0.01	0.01	0.99
Blood urea N	426	530	60	0.94	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.99
Citrulline	8.98	10.89	1.07	0.39	<0.01	0.01	<0.01	0.99
NH ₃	9.76	10.49	0.74	0.04	0.11	0.16	<0.01	0.52
Ornithine	4.48	4.26	0.43	0.68	<0.01	0.02	<0.01	0.86

408 ¹ α -AAA = α -amino adipic acid; 3-MH = 3-methylhistidine; 1-MH = 1-methylhistidine; PEA =

409 Phosphoethanolamine; EA = Ethanolamine; α -ABA = α -amino butyric acid.

410 ²*P*-value of the interactions (Treatment by Day and by Hour) belong to the comparison between the seven treatments.

411 ³*P*-value of the orthogonal contrast between the ad libitum (AL) and feed restricted (FR) diets.

412

413 Liver triglycerides infiltration post-calving takes place after NEFA concentration
 414 reaches its maximum concentration (Ohgi et al., 2005). In our study, the plasma
 415 concentration of triglycerides also decreased after concentration of NEFA reached its
 416 peak in blood, suggesting that hepatic infiltration of triglycerides might have started
 417 around d 3. The NEFA recently re-esterified into triglycerides must be exported from the
 418 liver. Despite ruminant species having a low capacity for triglycerides export from liver in
 419 comparison with non-ruminants (Pullen et al., 1990), we found a weak linear increase in
 420 the concentration of cholesterol, which suggests that cows under FR still maintained a
 421 proper hepatic function as expected in mid-lactation cows (Gross et al., 2015).

422 Even though cows in later stages of lactation have a less intense reaction to
 423 increase ketone bodies formation (Gross and Bruckmaier, 2015), we found that daily

424

425 **Table 10.** Least squares means of the concentrations ($\mu\text{mol/dL}$) of blood metabolites related with
 426 urea cycle and protein tissue mobilization of mid-lactation dairy cows during 5 days on the ad
 427 libitum (AL) and feed-restricted (FR) diets per day.

Item ¹	Diet	Day					SEM	P-values		
		1	2	3	4	5		Diet x Day ²	Trend ³	
								Lin.	Quad.	
1-MH	AL	0.93	0.99	1.03	1.02	1.04	0.09	0.47	0.14	0.32
	FR	0.94	0.95	1.01	1.00	0.94	0.07	0.27	0.59	0.03
3-MH	AL	0.17	0.18	0.17	0.18	0.24	0.08	0.11	0.14	0.22
	FR	0.15 ^d	0.19 ^c	0.26 ^b	0.29 ^a	0.31 ^a	0.05	<0.01	<0.01	0.31
Blood urea N	AL	489	516	527	533	487	53	0.38	0.92	0.08
	FR	450 ^b	579 ^a	556 ^a	494 ^b	493 ^b	39	<0.01	0.99	<0.01
Citrulline	AL	9.57	9.61	9.80	10.06	10.23	0.91	0.97	0.42	0.85
	FR	9.85 ^c	11.61	11.26 ^a	11.22 ^a	10.65 ^b	0.65	<0.01	0.44	<0.01
NH ₃	AL	9.98	9.92	9.82	9.52	9.55	0.79	0.91	0.27	0.98
	FR	10.4 ^a	10.7 ^b	10.5 ^{ab}	10.7 ^b	10.1 ^a	0.59	0.03	0.47	0.12
Ornithine	AL	4.66	4.46	4.60	4.41	4.27	0.51	0.83	0.54	0.85
	FR	5.03 ^a	4.33 ^b	4.08 ^b	4.04 ^b	3.82 ^b	0.38	<0.01	0.01	0.12

428 ¹ 3-MH = 3-methylhistidine; 1-MH = 1-methylhistidin.

429 ²P-value of the interaction of each diet (AL and FR) with day. Extracted from the SLICE statement output within the interaction of
 430 treatment with day.

431 ³P-values of the test for linear or quadratic trends.

432 Means in a row with superscripts without a common letter differ, $P \leq 0.05$.

433

434 BHB average reached its maximum at d 4, 1 day after the peak of NEFA
 435 concentration occurred. This asynchrony follows the biologic process previously
 436 mentioned wherein triglycerides infiltration and ketone bodies formation likely starts
 437 when NEFA uptake exceeded the capacity for triglycerides export and complete
 438 oxidation. In the fed state, BHB is the main ketone body synthesized by the liver and
 439 rumen epithelium. However, in the fasted state the BHB to acetoacetate ratio decreases
 440 (Heitmann et al., 1987) and acetoacetate can account for 20 to 30% of the total ketone
 441 body production in the liver (Katz and Bergman, 1969). Therefore, the magnitude of
 442 hepatic ketone body production in FR likely was underestimated.

443 An intense lipid mobilization would increase albumin demand to facilitate NEFA
444 uptake into tissues (Reist et al., 2003). The quadratic decline observed for albumin
445 points out the close relationship between NEFA and albumin as its carrier during
446 periods of fat mobilization (Seifi et al., 2007). On the other hand, serum albumin belongs
447 to the negative acute-phase proteins, whose production can be diminished by the effect
448 of cytokines (Bertoni et al., 2008). Cytokines are released around calving due to
449 diseases, stressors, or even nutritional imbalances (Drackley et al., 2005). Cytokines
450 have a major effect in liver characterized by the induction of positive acute phase
451 protein synthesis (e.g., haptoglobin) and the impairment of negative acute phase
452 synthesis (e.g., albumin; Bertoni et al., 2008). Furthermore, NEFA in serum also
453 competes with bilirubin for binding with albumin to be transported towards tissues such
454 as the liver (Listowsky et al., 1978). Therefore, the greater concentrations of bilirubin in
455 FR may be due to an impaired hepatic clearance due the lower availability of albumin
456 (Reid et al., 1983). In fact, there is a positive correlation of bilirubin in serum with liver
457 fat infiltration (West, 1990) and inflammation (Bertoni et al., 2008) in the transition
458 period. Nevertheless, this quick response of bilirubin to lipid mobilization makes it also a
459 good indicator of liver function during short periods of deprived feeding.

460 During the postprandial period, VFA from ruminal fermentation stimulate insulin
461 release, which will drive glucose toward insulin-sensitive cells (Allen et al., 2005),
462 thereby decreasing glucose concentration in plasma. However, the slightly greater
463 changes in insulin concentration after feeding during FR were not accompanied by
464 proportional decreasing changes in glucose concentration. This could indicates that,
465 even during a short-term of NNB, there is a reactive mechanism that reduces insulin

466 **Table 11.** Loadings in the first five factors extracted by
 467 factor analysis of all AA, urea cycle components and 3-
 468 methylhistidine in plasma.

Item	Rotated Factor Loadings ¹				
	Factor	Factor	Factor	Factor	Factor
3-MH	-	-	0.62	0.56	-
Ala	0.88	-0.09	-	-0.23	-
Arg	0.27	0.78	-	-	0.4
Asn	0.79	0.28	-0.26	-	0.35
Asp	-	0.45	-0.49	-0.52	-0.27
Blood urea N	-	-	0.83	-	-
Cit	0.34	0.42	0.55	0.4	0.25
Cys	-	0.3	-	0.77	-
Gln	-	-	-	-	0.85
Glu	-	0.32	-0.29	-0.7	-
Gly	-	0.38	-0.55	0.22	0.56
Hist	0.71	-	-	-	0.57
Ile	0.7	0.51	0.29	0.25	-
Leu	0.86	0.25	-	0.29	-
Lys	0.4	0.8	-	-	-
Met	0.71	0.48	-	-	-
NH ₃	0.36	-	-	-0.67	-
Orn	0.53	0.46	-	-	0.6
Phe	0.66	0.25	-0.55	-	-
Pro	0.89	-	0.01	-	0.33
Ser	0.63	-	-0.52	-	0.32
Thr	0.87	0.23	-	-	0.34
Trp	0.83	-	0.3	-	-
Tyr	0.89	-	-0.21	-	-
Val	0.8	0.27	0.25	0.38	-
Eigenvalue	10.74	4.35	2.46	1.8	1.18
Variance ² , %	42.9	17.4	9.8	7.2	4.7

469 ¹Correlations between the variable and the factor.

470 ²Non-cumulative variance explained by each factor.

471 Factor loadings smaller than |0.2| were omitted. Factor loadings in bold represent
 472 the greatest loading greater than |0.5| within each variable.

473

474 sensitivity in peripheral tissue (Marett et al., 2018b). This mechanism was also
475 reflected by a greater and increasing GIR (calculated only in samples before feeding)
476 during FR, which indicates that there could be a continuous state of peripheral insulin
477 resistance (Holtenius et al., 2003). The objective of this increase in insulin resistance
478 would be to allow a higher glucose uptake by the mammary gland when nutrients are
479 scarce (Gross et al., 2011).

480 *Protein-related blood metabolites*

481 The noticeable effect of FR on most AA concentrations reflected their demand
482 during short periods of NNB; therefore, identifying certain AA as potential biomarkers of
483 nutritional status and as targets for supplementation. In this section we discuss those
484 AA that were affected by the main effect of the diet especially the EAA, but it is
485 important to note that whether the diet alone or by through its interaction with day, all
486 AA were affected by feed restriction. The rapid increase of BUN and the balance
487 between the rise in BUN and the decrease in AA in circulation suggest that mobilization
488 of protein tissue may be a quick and important resource to supply energy precursors to
489 maintain milk production and requirements for maintenance.

490 Since Pro is one of the AA with greatest abundance in the body, due to its
491 function in collagen synthesis, its demand may overcome supply in certain scenarios. In
492 a nutrient stress situation, Pro can be metabolized to yield Glu and then α -ketoglutarate
493 (**α -KG**), which can participate in gluconeogenesis. The Pro concentration in plasma
494 usually declines around parturition and then increases quickly in early lactation (Maeda
495 et al., 2012). However, Laeger et al. (2012) and Kuhla et al. (2011) did not find any
496 variation of Pro after feed restriction.

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Figure 1. Concentrations of insulin, glucose, nonesterified fatty acids (NEFA), β -hydroxy-butyrate (BHB), essential (EAA) and non-essential amino acids (NEAA) in plasma averaged across the 5-d period at -1, 0, +3, +4, +5 and +14 h after feeding during ad libitum (AL) and feed restricted diets (FR). Concentrations at same time points with different letter are significantly different. Differences between diets are marked at each time point with † ($P < 0.10$) and * ($P < 0.05$).

527 Enzymatic conversion from Phe to Tyr is increased by glucagon and inhibited by
528 insulin, while catabolism of Tyr is induced by cortisol and other glucocorticoid
529 hormones. Therefore, during FR it seems that a greater degradation of Phe and Tyr
530 may have be triggered by the decrease in insulin (Ansia et al. unpublished results) and
531 the likely increase in plasma cortisol concentration (Toerien and Cant, 2007), driving
532 their catabolism towards gluconeogenesis from these AA and reducing their protein
533 synthesis potential (Doepel et al., 2016). Laeger et al. (2012) found a tendency for a
534 lower plasma concentration of Tyr and a lower Tyr concentration in cerebrospinal fluid,
535 which would suggest a potential central anorexic effect. Tyrosine is also a precursor of
536 thyroid hormones in the thyroid gland, as well as neurotransmitters (catecholamines)
537 and hormone precursor in neurons and adrenal medulla, respectively. Among
538 catecholamines, adrenaline, noradrenaline, and dopamine have a recognized anorexic
539 effect that would help counteract hunger. Although during FR periods synthesis of
540 thyroid hormones seems to decrease, catecholamines in circulation increase to reduce
541 milk production and increase lipogenesis (Salin et al., 2017).

542 Laeger et al. (2012) reported a similar reduction (-12%) to ours in plasma Thr
543 concentration and an even larger decrease in the cerebrospinal fluid concentration of
544 Thr (-24%), which suggests that Thr could also act as a signal for feed intake regulation.
545 Alike most of the EAA, Thr concentration also decreases as calving approaches and
546 increases as lactation advances (Larsen et al., 2015). Reduction of Thr has been
547 reported consistently in short periods of FR (Baird et al., 1972; Kuhla et al., 2011).
548 Addition of extra Thr through abomasal infusions in early lactation did not have a
549 positive effect, but neither did its deletion cause a negative consequence (Doepel et al.,

550 2016). This outcome suggests that even on a low protein intake, the cow would be able
551 to meet its Thr requirements.

552 An increase or no variation in Gly concentration during NNB has been reported in
553 the literature during short-term feed restriction periods (Kuhla et al., 2011; Laeger et al.,
554 2012) or during the transition period (Larsen and Kristensen, 2009), whereas Baird et al.
555 (1972) reported a non-significant decrease (-27%) after 6 d of complete starvation. This
556 common observation could be due to a reduced mammary (Raggio et al., 2006) and
557 hepatic (Larsen and Kristensen, 2009) uptake, and to a net release triggered by tissue
558 mobilization. Glycine is the backbone of the basic unit that form connective tissue, and
559 is also one of the AA with greatest abundance in muscle in its free form (Meijer et al.,
560 1995). Sarcosine is a direct precursor of Gly and its concentration was also increased
561 during FR in this study; therefore, it is likely that the sarcosine pathway was active
562 during FR.

563 Lysine uptake is greater than its milk output and occurs mostly in the mammary
564 gland (Mephram, 1982). Oxidation of Lys provides the N-group for synthesis of other
565 NEAA such as Arg and Pro. An increase in Lys concentration during feed restriction has
566 been commonly reported (Baird et al., 1972; Kuhla et al., 2011; Laeger et al., 2012).
567 The decrease of milk protein production suggests that Lys would not be demanded for
568 this anabolic process since the mammary gland has the capacity to alter AA uptake to
569 meet its requirements (Mackle et al., 2000). Guo et al. (2017) found that mammary Lys
570 clearance and the ratio mammary uptake:milk output only decreased significantly when
571 all Lys supply was removed. This result indicates that there could be a compensatory
572 mechanism to supply a certain amount of Lys to the mammary gland even with low

573 nutritional supply. In fact, post-hepatic supply is greater than mammary uptake
574 regardless of the portal net absorption of Lys, and mammary uptake decreases by only
575 a small proportion relative to a reduced post-hepatic supply (Lapierre et al., 2009). A
576 reduction in hepatic uptake could explain why plasma Lys concentration tended to be
577 higher during FR, if the mammary uptake was still maintained. However, uptake of Lys
578 for milk protein synthesis could have been reduced in favor of catabolism toward
579 synthesis of other NEAA such as Arg and Pro (Lapierre et al., 2009; Guo et al., 2017).
580 The most common pathway for Lys catabolism is the saccharopine pathway, which
581 uses α -amino adipic acid (α -AAA) as intermediate. High concentrations of α -AAA
582 despite the elevated concentrations of Lys during FR could in fact suggest that hepatic
583 and extrahepatic oxidation are part of the regulatory mechanism to control the excess of
584 Lys in circulation (Tucker et al., 2017).

585 Mammary gland takes up Arg at a higher rate than milk output as well. Its
586 catabolism contributes to milk protein synthesis and as AA precursor (Clark et al.,
587 1978). As demonstrated in vitro, Arg plays a crucial role in protein synthesis as regulator
588 of transcription in casein and m-TOR pathway genes in mammary epithelial cells (Wang
589 et al., 2014). If regulation of the mammary extraction efficiency involves specific AA
590 transporters (Mackle et al., 2000), Lys and Arg could have been equally affected during
591 FR because they share almost exclusively (with ornithine to some extent) the same
592 unique cationic transporter (Y^+) across mammary tissue membranes (Baumrucker,
593 1984), which would explain the greater plasma concentration of both AA during FR.
594 Therefore, the reduction in milk protein synthesis caused by the endocrine changes
595 during NNB could be either triggered by or augmented by disabled transport of Lys and

596 Arg into the mammary gland. In fact, Rius et al. (2010) found that only abomasal
597 infusion of starch (with that concomitant raise of insulin and IGF-1 concentrations)
598 rather than casein during feed restriction was able to stimulate mammary AA uptake
599 and milk protein synthesis despite excess availability of AA.

600 In other studies similar to ours, His concentration did not decrease during feed
601 restriction (Baird et al., 1972; Laeger et al., 2012), or even was higher (Kuhla et al.,
602 2011). However, in early lactation His seems to undergo a high uptake by the mammary
603 gland (Larsen et al., 2015), causing a prolonged deficiency since arterial levels did not
604 return to pre-calving concentrations during the time-frame of most studies (Meijer et al.,
605 1995; Doepel et al., 2002). Histidine in body tissue is methylated when the muscle
606 contractile proteins are broken down during protein mobilization. This new form, 3-MH,
607 cannot be recycled for protein synthesis and thus has to be excreted, becoming an
608 optimal index of tissue protein turnover (Doepel et al., 2002). However, 3-MH plasma
609 concentration is not a proportional indicator of amount of muscle mobilized because its
610 incomplete recovery in urine suggests a pool of non-protein bound 3-MH in muscle
611 (Lobley, 1998). 1-Methylhistidine is another methylated form of His that in combination
612 with β -alanine forms anserine, which is a methylated form of carnosine present in
613 skeletal muscle that also has anorexigenic effects (Tomonaga et al., 2004). While 3-MH
614 and 1-MH must be excreted, β -alanine can be catabolized to yield acetyl-CoA in tissues.
615 During the FR diet, daily averages of carnosine (-9%) and β -alanine (-15%) showed
616 similar patterns of decrease that matched the increase of 1-MH (+8%). The same
617 opposite pattern across time between carnosine and 1-MH was reported by Laeger et
618 al. (2012). These results could indicate that carnosine in muscle likely was degraded

619 during FR, releasing β -alanine that also would be catabolized and 1-MH that would be
620 excreted.

621 Since dietary N intake was reduced, the increase of BUN during FR indicates
622 that the urea cycle was in motion to eliminate excess N produced by AA catabolism or
623 as result of N recycling from the digestive tract to use endogenous urea as N source.
624 Higher BUN concentrations also were reported during feed-restriction conditions in
625 other experiments (Loor et al., 2007; Kuhla et al., 2011). The rapid response of BUN to
626 FR probably could have contributed to hide this effect in other studies with FR (Carlson
627 et al., 2006; Laeger et al., 2012), or even during the onset of lactation (Zhu et al., 2000),
628 where sampling was as frequent. In addition, plasma ammonia concentration is
629 probably a better indicator of AA catabolism than BUN during the transition period
630 because expression of some of the enzymes involved in ureagenesis is decreased at
631 calving and does not seem to react accordingly with the requirements at the onset of
632 lactation (Hartwell et al., 2001).

633 Both Glu and Asp play an important role as they are involved in the urea and
634 tricarboxylic acid cycles, both highly active because of their implications for AA
635 catabolism and gluconeogenesis during periods of NNB (Noro and Wittwer, 2012).
636 Glutamate provides α -KG, an intermediate in the tricarboxylic acid cycle, and the α -
637 amino N required to synthesize Asp from oxaloacetate. The synchronized and opposite
638 patterns across days for BUN and Gln during FR seems to elucidate that urea formation
639 was the predominant method at the beginning of dietary restriction, probably due to the
640 greater detoxification capacity of ammonia at lower energetic cost (Reynolds, 2006).
641 However, as days pass urea synthesis seemed to decrease and Gln synthesis

642 increased, suggesting a switch towards the low-capacity, high-affinity method to detoxify
643 ammonia as Gln (Lobley et al., 1995). This shift could have been established to save
644 bicarbonate ions and maintain an adequate cation-anion balance (Meijer et al., 1993).

645 The increase in BUN coincided with the steepest decrease in plasma
646 concentrations of most AA. We acknowledge that these estimates are not quantitative
647 because fluxes of compounds and differential half-lives in circulation were not
648 measured. However, accounting for the balance of N compounds measured in plasma
649 by comparing incremental area under the curve (IAUC) of the N-elements whose
650 concentration increased from d 1 to d 5 (N-AA⁺) and BUN, with those whose
651 concentration decreased (N-AA⁻), there seemed to be a shortfall of amino-N sources for
652 the increase in BUN. Considering the limitations of this rough comparative method,
653 during AL we observed a quite well balanced equilibrium between the positive IAUC of
654 N-AA⁺ (56 µg·d) and BUN (735 µg·d) in plasma, and the negative IAUC of N-AA⁻ (-544
655 µg·d). However, during FR the IAUC of BUN (2,266 µg·d) and N-AA⁺ (207 µg·d)
656 increased when compared with the AL diet to a much greater degree (2x) than the IAUC
657 of N-AA⁻ (-1,135 µg·d).

658 During short periods of feed restriction hepatic uptake of lactate seems to not
659 play a great role as a precursor for gluconeogenesis (Laeger et al., 2012), unlike in
660 early lactation (Larsen and Kristensen, 2012). Therefore, tissue mobilization and
661 peptides in circulation probably could have contributed to the AA turnover and
662 catabolism, being then the source of that “extra” BUN during FR. In accordance with the
663 literature, plasma proteins, liver protein, and gastrointestinal tract tissue would be the
664 first mobilized (Swick and Benevenga, 1977), while skeletal muscle breakdown probably

665 would be more intense at the end of the period as the increasing concentrations of 3-
666 MH and α -AAA in plasma indicated in our study.

667 *Exploratory factor analysis*

668 Factor analysis allowed us to reduce some of the principal variables involved in
669 protein metabolism (individual AA, NH_3 , BUN, and 3-MH) into a reduced number of
670 factors identifying underlying correlations among those variables. Loadings of factor 1
671 confirm the common effect of FR over all the EAA except Lys and Arg, plus the NEAA
672 Ser, Ala, Tyr, Asn, and Pro, whose concentrations were reduced during FR. Factor 2
673 loadings demonstrate that FR provoked a different effect over Lys and Arg than over the
674 majority of EAA, and emphasizes their mutual correlation as previously discussed. Due
675 to the required inter-organ coordination during ureagenesis, Cit concentration, rather
676 than Arg, probably determines better the concentration of BUN since both were grouped
677 in factor 3. In addition, the correlation of BUN with 3-MH within factor 3 reveals that the
678 catabolism of tissue could be an important source of the N captured and excreted as
679 urea. Factor 4 indicates the different evolution of the increasing concentrations of Cys,
680 and elucidates the coordinated demand for Asp and Glu in the urea cycle as shown by
681 their correlation with NH_3 (Noro and Wittwer, 2012). Lastly, grouping of Gln and Gly
682 within factor 5 could suggest a similar effect over their release from muscle upon tissue
683 breakdown. Glutamine has the highest concentration in muscle as free AA (Meijer et al.,
684 1995) and Gly is omnipresent in the tri-peptide that forms the basic unit in connective
685 tissue; therefore, their higher concentration could be indicative of a release upon muscle
686 degradation (Doepel et al., 2002).

687 **Conclusions**

688 The decrease in insulin concentration during FR coordinately triggered lipid and
689 AA mobilization and oxidation as reflected by the greater NEFA and BUN
690 concentrations in plasma and milk. Protein tissue mobilization and modulation of tissue
691 insulin sensitivity may be important mechanisms to supply N and energy substrates for
692 metabolic fuel, and NEFA and glucose for milk synthesis, respectively, during a short
693 period of restricted DMI. Results from our model highlight the need for more research to
694 better understand the role of protein tissue catabolism and endocrine regulation in
695 shorts periods of NNB.

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699 **Ethics statement**

700 All procedures involving animals were approved by the Institutional Animal Care
701 and Use Committee at the University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign (protocol #15167).

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